

IMPACT OF GLOBALISATION ON INDIAN MEDIA AND ENTERTAINMENT INDUSTRY

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Introduction:

The Indian media and entertainment industry is one of the fastest growing industry in the world. India has many entertainment media. Its film and television sectors are dominating the entertainment industry. Film and television sectors are growing and globalisation has impacted entertainment and media sectors. India produces many films running at global level theatres, especially in Japan, Singapore, USA, and Canada. Indian films and televisions got very large audience all over the world. Indian film and television producers are improving the international marketability of large budget Indian movies by building partnership with international screenwriters and composers technicians.

This article is an attempt to highlight the impact of globalisation on Indian media and entertainment industry. Indian film industry enjoys world fourth place and television industry is in the third place. The Indian Media and Entertainment Industry is among the fastest growing sectors in the country.¹

The most important effect of Globalisation on film industries was that it enabled a bigger market for films worldwide. It was after the 1990's that films started to get released worldwide. This increased the size of the film market and massive growth of revenue in result. The gross profit that Hollywood generated in the year 1997 was \$30 billion, where Titanic alone contributing more \$1.8 billion.²

Indian Film Industry:

The first Indian feature film was produced in the year 1913. That was raja harishchandra produced by prominent theatre artist dada sahib phalke. Indian film industry had worked just like the Hollywood until the 1960's. Artists had worked on contractual basis for particular studio. It was after the 1900's that artists started to work on a freelance basis.

India had produced 1288 films in 2009,³ which was around 24% of the films produced worldwide. Please see table 1. The amount of films produced in India was almost the double than that production in the United States of America (677films in 2009, which is around 12% of the world share). The cost of production of films in India is much lower than many other developed countries. When developed countries produce films for billions of dollars, India does it in millions. According to *Screen Australia* (2010) the total production cost of Indian films in 2010 was just \$195 million, whereas that in U.S.A was \$13,289 million.

Table - 1

Rank (2009)	Country	Number of Feature Films Produced				
		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
1.	India	1,041	1,016	1,164	1,325	1,288
2.	US	699	673	909	716	677
3.	China	260	330	402	406	456
4.	Japan	356	417	407	418	448
5.	France	240	203	228	240	230

shodhganga.inflibnet.ac/bitstream/10603/3433/08-chapter V

Suraj films.blogspot.com/2011/01/influence-of-globalisation-on-indian-html

Ibid., p. 3

6.	Spain	142	150	172	173	186
7.	Germany	103	122	122	125	150
8.	South Korea	87	110	124	113	139
9.	Italy	98	116	121	154	131
10.	UK	131	134	117	111	126

Source: Suraj films.blogspot.com/2011/01/influence-of-globalisation-on-indian-html

As per this table it has been observed that Indian film industry is playing a dominant role in films making in 2005. India overtook USA, china and UK by 33%, 75% and in 2007 by 47%, 65% and 90% it shows the greatness of Indian film industry. As per 2009 we make 3 to 4 average films every day. While America and china are very less as compare to India.

Growth of the Indian Entertainment and Media Industry 2006 – 10:

The Indian and media and entrainment industry in India has been and will continue to be one of the biggest beneficiaries of India’s favourable demographics. Being one of the youngest nations in the world, with high volumes of content consumption, a vibrant indigenous content creation industry and a favourable regulatory frame work, makes India an attractive investment destination for global media entertainment sectors¹. The Entertainment and Media Industry 2010 stood at INR 646.0 billion as compared to INR 580.8 billion in 2009. This was lower than our projected growth rate of 15.1% for last year. The reason for lower growth rate was the decline witnessed in the film segment. The other two key industry segments-- television (15.4% growth as compared to 15.6% projected) and print (10.7% as compared to 8.5% projected)-- showed good growth. Please see the table. 2

The negative growth in the film segment for a second year in a row was largely due to the lack of quality content and the closing-down of single-screen theatres.

Table - 2: Growth of the M&E Industry in (2006 – 10)

INR billion	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	CDGR
Television	191.2	223.9	244.7	265.5	306.5	12.5
% change		17.1	9.3	8.5	15.4	
Film	84.5	96.0	107.0	95.0	87.5	0.9
% change		13.6	11.5	-11.2	-7.9	
Print	128.0	149.0	162.0	161.5	178.7	8.7
% change		16.4	8.7	-0.3	10.7	
Radio	5.0	6.9	8.3	9.0	10.8	21.2
% change		38.0	20.3	8.4	20.0	
Internet	12.6	2.7	5.0	6.0	7.7	48.1
% change		68.8	85.2	20.0	28.3	
OOH	10.0	12.5	15.0	12.5	14.0	8.8
% change		25.0	20.0	-6.7	12.0	
Animation, , gaming & VFX	12.6	15.7	19.6	23.8	31.3	25.6
% change		24.6	24.6	21.8	31.4	
Music	7.3	7.6	6.9	7.5	9.5	6.8
% change		3.8	-8.2	8.5	25.7	
Total	440.02	514.3	568.5	580.8	646.0	10.1
% change		16.8	10.5	2.2	11.2	

Source: Indian Entertainment and Media Outlook, 2011.

Effects of Globalisation on the Indian Film Production Industry:

Formation of international joint- ventured production houses was one of the main effects of Globalisation. Mostly the ventures were between Hollywood an Indian production houses. ‘Studio 18’ is an example for that. It is a joint venture between

John Nendik and farokh T.Balsara,spot light on india’s entertainment economy,Ernst&young,p.8.,

'Viacom' a U.S. based communication company and 'Network 18', an India based media conglomerate. Studio18 has produced a total of 15 films and have released it worldwide

Another effect of globalisation was the absorption of small Indian studios by large International production houses. This has acted both in positive ways and negative. The positive factor is that many artists get to work with an international company. But, unfortunately the negative side is that is not what happens most of the time. An example of such absorption was the Sony Pictures taking over the Chennai based animation studio 'Image works'. It was definitely for the good of the company because later it had largely contributed to films like Spiderman 3 and I am Legend.

In the recent years a lot of international producers have put in money directly into single films. Sony Pictures in 2007 associated with Sanjay Leela Bhansali, directly entered into the market producing a Hindi film named Saawariya. Though Saawariya was not a commercial success in India, the film grossed \$805,054 in U.S.A alone (I.M.D.B, 2007). Later in 2009 Warner Brothers produced a film associating with Ramesh Sippy Entertainment named Chandini Chowk to China. The film grossed around \$1 million from U.S.A alone (I.M.D.B, 2009).

Exchange of Talent:

Globalisation has helped the film production companies to share the international pool of talent. The rate of usage of international talent increased tremendously after the 1990's. Later, many artists from international cinema have worked for Indian cinema and vice versa.

International Artists Worked in Indian Films:

Danny Pierce: Stunt coordinator Danny Pierce (films like: The Pirates of the Caribbean) had recently worked for an Indian film 'Kites'. Snoop Dog: Hip-hop artist Snoop Dog had worked on the sound track of a Hindi film named Singh is King. The film is considered to be a hit in the U.K. A studio that recently worked for an Indian film was the Stan Winston Studios for Enthiran. They had worked on the animatronics. According to Indo Asian News service (2010), Enthiran is the most expensively produced film among Indian films. The film which spent around \$38 million was produced in two different languages, Hindi and Tamil.

Indian Artists Worked in International Films:

A.R.Rahman¹ who composed and produced music for the film Slumdog Millionaire and Resul Pookutty who mixed the sound for the same film are one of the main examples. A major studio that contributed and is still contributing to international films is the Ramoji film city in Hyderabad, India. It is in fact the world's largest integrated film studio complex. It provides locations, lights, grip equipment, camera, production crew, set designs, props & costumes and post production (Processing, editing, mixing, printing & duplicating). More than 15 international projects have been worked in Ramoji Film city so far. As described in their Credo Ramoji believes that film-makers can, "walk in with a script and walk out with a canned film." (Ramoji Film City, no date).

Television Industry in India:

- ✓ Television sector is one of the major mass media of India.
- ✓ India is the second - longest pay - TV market in the world, with 108 million subscribers and a reach of 48% of Indian households.²

Suraj films.blogspot.com/2011/01/influence-of-globalisation-on-indian.html

Dr. Tapan Kumar Nayak and Gaurav Rastogi, Role of Film and TV Industry in our Economy, Ghaziabad, 1990, p.10

- ✓ It is a huge industry which has thousands of programmes across Indian sates ranging from national language to regional ones.
- ✓ The small screen has produced numerous celebrities of their own kind some even attaining national fame.
- ✓ Approximately half of all Indian household own a television.
- ✓ As of 2010, the country has a collection of free and subscription services over a variety of distribution media. Through which there are over 515 channels and 150 are pay channels.
- ✓ According to pioneer invest Corp, the Indian cable industry is worth ` 270 billion (US \$ 5.94 billion) and is the largest in the world after China and the US.
- ✓ The number of TV homes in India grew from 120 million in 2007 to 148 million 2011.
- ✓ Cable reaches 94 million homes with 88 million analog connections and 6 million digital ones, while DTH has commanded 41 million subscribers.

Prospects of Indian Television Industry:

Increased fragmentation in Viewership: Viewership, especially in the Hindi general entertainment gave is increasingly getting fragmented as a result of a large number of such channels being broadcast in India. However, a few players continue to dominate the market, commanding a significant share of the industry segment revenues.

Increased Competition Amongst Broadcasters: With new channels being introduced at regular intervals, there is increased competition amongst broadcasters, for viewership and advertising revenues. This coupled with high content and marketing cost is expected to impact the profitability of broadcasters in the medium and long term.

Increased Penetration of DTH (Direct to Home): There has been rapid growth of DTH subscribers in the last few years. This trend is expected to continue over the next few years. However, operating profits are still negative for the industry, due to high customer acquisition costs and is expected to remain this way until a critical mass of subscribers is reached. Major DTH service providers in India are: Dish TV, Airtel Digital, Reliance Digital, Videocon, Sun TV, Tata Sky.¹

Impact of Television:

The influence of television in learning mechanism is considered to be very significant. In Urban Rural society, where a substantial portion of the population are compelled to communicate in language other than their own. A visual medium like television is considered to be a more useful means of learning and communicating cultural ideas than the spoken or a written world. The impact of television may not always be positive. Now, let us discuss the types of influence this medium exerts on our ways of life.

Positive Aspect:

- ✓ Television programmes are most informative and educative if we watch programmes like UGC programmes, quiz programmes and also group discussions. Thus, we can say that it is a medium for acquiring information, knowledge and understanding.
- ✓ Now - a - days, everywhere in our country, Hindi has become a household language.² Everyone starts speaking Hindi besides one's own mother tongue whether it is Oriya, Bengali or Telugu. This is only because of regular watching

ibid,, p.16.

<http://www.tezu.ernet.in/dmass/Students%20Corner/Abhijit%20Bora%20Course%20Outline/Mass%20media,%20Culture%20and%20Democracy.pdf>

Television. Television is thus the need for strengthening contacts with family, friends and others.

- ✓ It satisfies our need to know what is going on in and around the world. Television reveals dresses of different communities, food of people from South India to North India and also the rituals and religious practices of people from different corners of the country.
- ✓ Television is the source of entertainment to people of all categories. It provides company for the lonely, aged, and housewives. It gives topics for conversation to number of the family staying at home. For the working people it's a tension release mechanism, affording an easy diversion from problems and from routines of life.

Negative Aspect:

- ✓ There are few areas where the influence of television is not positive. It is found that the naked exposures to sensuality. The criminal items and unfair possism by anti - social elements of society exercise the most adverse impact on children in particular and the youth in general. Many of the scenes and themes shown, on TV in films, serials, advertisements, interview, and cultural themes, for which our traditional national culture stood. But it dehumanizes the views by naked exposure to sensuality, criminality, militancy, unfairness and several other negative aspect of it.
- ✓ The sheer amount of time spent in watching TV by the children is often too large. Thus they have negative impact in terms of their studies, socialization and participation in other entertainment activities.¹
- ✓ In our present day society, with an increasing wave to crime and violence we are beginning to look at the relationship between television programmes and cultural values more clearly. In a recent study of TV programmes, in three metros of India, the following result was found.
- ✓ Out of 3,500 children, 79 per cent prefer to watch cartoon network as entertainment rather than any educational programme. 11 per cent prefer national geography channel on 8 per cent prefer family serials and 2 per cent have no specification for any programme.
- ✓ A maximum number of children prefer cartoon network as the main channel of entertainment. It is now time to telecast Indian cultural values through cartoon channels. Epics like Ramayana, Mahabharata, Bhagvat Geetha and Stories of Panchatantra should come up in cartoon channels. Stories with strong historical back ground like that of Tipu Sultan, Shivajee and Bhagavat Singh should reach children through entertainment channels. Television is becoming increasingly important as an institution for socialising the younger members of Indian society. The role of TV in moulding their minds and teaching them Indian values and Indian way of life is growing at startling rate.

Prospects of Indian Film Industry:

Growth is expected to come from the expansion of multiplexes in smaller cities, investments by foreign studios in domestic and regional productions, the growing popularity of niche movies and the emergence of digital and ancillary streams.

Rise of Multiplexes: Multiplexes continue to gain prominences across major Indian cities and companies have lined up investments to accelerate multiplex

ibid., p. 23.

penetration in smaller towns. The number of multiplex screens is expected to double in the next five years, from 900 to 1,775 screens.

Globalization and India:

India is one of the world's largest markets for satellite TV, with some 300 million viewers. The Indian economy opened up in the 1990s after decades of being closed. (Pressure came from western and international institutions such as the IMF, World Bank, etc.)

This led to an explosion in global consumer goods. There was also an explosion in Indian television. While globalization of television has been going on since the 1980s (with the likes of CNN, MTV, Sky, Star TV, etc),¹ in India, demand from urban middle classes came around 1991 for the likes of CNN for coverage of international events such as the first Gulf War.

Star TV (a Hong Kong based company, owned by Rupert Murdoch's News Corp and present in many, many Asian countries) found it easy to penetrate in India. This was because of many reasons, including that The existing broadcast was based on an old system The existing broadcast was state-owned primarily a vehicle for news, education, and social issues, such as how to deal with various health.

Role or Importance of Film and Television Industry in our Economy:

Film and TV industry is one of the important contributors to the economy and plays a very important and critical role in economic development due to the following reasons.

- ✓ Contribution of film and TV to the GDP was 0.532%.
- ✓ The combined revenues of film and TV industry was around ` 50,000 crore (USD 10,00 billion) in the calendar year 2011. It is expected that will be around ` 54,000 crore (USD 11,00 billion) in the calendar year 2012.
- ✓ The film and television industry in India is one of the world's largest markets in terms of number of consumers and offers significant growth potential.
- ✓ Over the past few years the industry has experienced rapid double – digit growth and it is expected that this trend will continue in future, resulting in increasing contribution to the Indian economy.
- ✓ The sector has a total output more than \$ 20 billion (1,00,000crore), contributing more to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of India than the advertising industry.
- ✓ Film and TV industry creates more than 2 million jobs (directly and indirectly) in the economy.

Problems of Piracy:

Piracy is the main problem in the film industry. Piracy in the industry is in the form of physical CD sales and online film download. India is among the top five countries in the world, in terms of piracy. Piracy mainly happens through file-sharing networks. The number of portals providing films online for free has also increased has also increased manifold in the last year.

Major Indian studios have formed a coalition named alliance against copyright theft to fight piracy. The alliance has reliance big entertainment, moser bear entertainment UTV Motion pictures, Eros International and the movie producers and distributors Association as its members. Since its formation, it has conducted multiple raids in Mumbai and Gujarat. However, the lack of strict anti-piracy laws means culprits

can get away with mild punishment. The government is required to do more if piracy has to be brought under control.¹

Conclusion:

Indian film and television industry produced many films and television programmes. Indian film and television actors are working all over the world and gaining fame. To produce more films it is good for our economic growth. Indian film industry has played a significant role to modernise the society and it has also contributed in social and economic development directly and indirectly. Some negative impacts of the television and media have also been observed on the society, which need concerns. Censorship should be stronger to prevent negativity in Indian television and media. Indian film industry has been developing since 1913. Indian film and television industry meet the main problem of piracy and Indian government should take necessary steps to stop the piracy so that the future of the industry can be saved.

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